

XXIII.—*On the Disruptive Discharge of Electricity: An Experimental Thesis for the Degree of Doctor of Science, Department A.* By ALEXANDER MACFARLANE, M.A., B.Sc. (Plate XXIII.)

(Read 18th February 1878.)

The experiments to which I shall refer were carried out in the physical laboratory of the University during the late summer session. I was ably assisted in conducting the experiments by three students of the laboratory,—Messrs H. A. SALVESEN, G. M. CONNOR, and D. R. STEWART. The method which was used of measuring the difference of potential required to produce a disruptive discharge of electricity under given conditions, is that described in a paper communicated to the Royal Society of Edinburgh in 1876 in the names of Mr J. A. PATON, M.A., and myself,* and was suggested to me by Professor TAIT as a means of attacking the experimental problems mentioned below.

The above sketch which I took of the apparatus *in situ* may facilitate the description of the method. The receiver of an air-pump, having a rod capable of being moved air-tight up and down through the neck, was attached to one of the conductors of a Holtz machine in such a manner that the conductor of the machine and the rod formed one conducting system. Projecting from the bottom of the receiver was a short metallic rod, forming one conductor

* "Proc. R.S.E." vol. ix. p. 332.

with the metallic parts of the air-pump, and by means of a chain with the uninsulated conductor of the Holtz machine. Brass balls and discs of various sizes were made to order, capable of being screwed on to the ends of the rods. On the table, and at a distance of about six feet from the receiver, was a stand supporting two insulated brass balls, the one fixed, the other having one degree of freedom, viz., of moving in a straight line in the plane of the table. The fixed insulated ball A was made one conductor with the insulated conductor of the Holtz and the rod of the receiver, by means of a copper wire insulated with gutta percha, having one end stuck firmly into a hole in the collar of the receiver, and having the other fitted in between the glass stem and the hollow in the ball, by which it fitted on to the stem tightly. A thin wire similarly fitted in between the ball B and its insulating stem connected the ball with the insulated half ring of a divided ring reflecting electrometer.

Thus there were in all four conducting systems,—*First*, the interior surface of the room, with the uninsulated conductor of the Holtz, the lower electrode inside the receiver, the outside case and the uninsulated half of the divided ring of the electrometer. *Second*, the insulated conductor of the Holtz, with the rod of the receiver, the upper electrode, the covered wire, and fixed insulated ball. *Third*, the movable insulated ball, with the wire and insulated half of the divided ring of the electrometer. *Fourth*, the Leyden jar of the electrometer, with the vertical wire and horizontal needle. To keep these four systems of conductors insulated from one another was a condition essential to accuracy in the experiments. To satisfy this condition the two glass insulating stems A and B were thoroughly heated each morning before the fire, the upper part of the receiver was coated with shellac, while the lower part was coated in the inside with tinfoil, connected by a strip with the lower rod. The fourth system was generally charged before taking a series of observations by communicating to it a half-inch spark from the electrophorus. Its insulation was several times tested by taking two observations, distant by the lapse of twenty-four hours, of the reading at discharge under conditions constant, excepting as to the charge of the moving needle. I find that the readings on the 30th and 31st May for a spark $\cdot 5$ centimetre long, and under given conditions, were 99 and 79.6 respectively; from which we may infer that four-fifths of the charge remained after a lapse of twenty-four hours.

When the potential of the second system was raised by driving the machine, the potential of the third was also raised; and this went on until a discharge took place between the electrodes inside the receiver, so that the deflection of the spot of light from zero was an indication of the difference of potential of the second and first systems when the discharge took place. By breaking the contact between the conductors of the Holtz machine before beginning to turn the wheel, and by turning the wheel slowly and steadily, we made the image of the wire move continuously, and to be at rest at the instant of dis-

charge. After the discharge took place the image fell back and oscillated about zero or a point near it.

The force resisting the deflection of the mirror was the action of two external magnets upon several small magnets fixed to the back of the mirror. The two external magnets were at the beginning of the experiments properly placed on the top of the case, and kept by melted paraffin in the same positions throughout.

The distance between the electrodes, where the spark passed, was measured by resting a finely divided glass millimetre scale on the flat surface of the collar of the receiver, and adjusting the rod until a thin wire soldered to a ring forming the upper part of the rod coincided with a scratch on the scale. For some time we had no other means of inferring the pressure of the insulator inside the receiver than the indications of a gauge, the greatest range of which was 200 mms.; but finally we had a barometer tube in connection.

When the second system of conductors is charged to a positive potential, the potential of the third system is also positive, but necessarily less than that of the first. By increasing the distance between the balls A and B, the potential of the latter system may be reduced to any fraction of the potential of the former. Were this lessening not made, the potentials which formed the subject of the research would be too great to be measured by any electrometer. To ascertain minutely the law according to which the potential of the third system diminished when the distance of the ball B from the ball A was increased, I took the series of observations recorded in Tables I. and II., and plotted on figs. 7 and 8. The insulated balls used in the series of observations of 29th May were of unequal diameters—2·5 inches and 2 inches respectively; and they were supported by slightly dissimilar stems. They were replaced on the 12th June by the balls and stand represented in the sketch, and which were specially constructed for the purpose. The new balls are each of 2·25 inches diameter. The slide on which the ball B moves is graduated to half millimetres, so that its position during any series of observations can be accurately recorded. It was generally 42·75 centimetres, sometimes 32·75 centimetres.

In addition to the difference in the balls, the constants were very different, being in the one case the difference of potential required to pass a spark between two ball electrodes of one inch diameter through 6 centimetres of air at a pressure of 160 mm.; and in the other between two discs 4 inches diameter through ·5 centimetre of air at 740 mm. pressure. Yet the equations expressing the dependence of the potential of the third system upon the distance between the centres of the insulated balls, are very similar. In the case of the first curve, the equation $V = 4522 \cdot 6r^{-1} - 20 \cdot 24$, where V denotes the induced potential on the ball B, and r the distance of its centre from the centre of the ball A, satisfies all the observed values of r beyond 22·5 centimetres; while the equation

$$V = 2903 \cdot 5r^{-1} + 58 \cdot 073 - \cdot 31807r,$$

got by multiplying the former function of r by $\cdot 642 + \frac{\cdot 11}{7}r$, satisfies all the observed values up to 22·5 centimetres ; and in the case of the second curve, the equation

$$V = 6081\cdot 7r^{-1} - 42\cdot 262$$

satisfies all the values of r beyond 24 centimetres ; while the equation

$$V = 3188\cdot 4r^{-1} + 98\cdot 32 - \cdot 83970r,$$

got by multiplying the former function of r by $\cdot 52427 + \cdot 019822r$, satisfies all the preceding observed values. The figures show these peculiarities well. As the curve is not discontinuous, the true function of r for V must coincide with the former function when r is large, and with the latter when r is small. The observations of 20th July, where a single observation was taken for each value of r , may be taken as showing the degree of precision finally arrived at in the experiments.

In the sketch there is represented on the corner of the table a long range absolute electrometer, which the Professor of Natural Philosophy procured on loan for me from Sir WILLIAM THOMSON, for the purpose of reducing the results to absolute measure. To provide for this reduction, I took each day four or five observations of the reading given when a spark passed between the two parallel metal discs at a distance of $\cdot 5$ centimetre, the insulating air being at the pressure of the atmosphere. I compared the electrometers on five days by the following method :—I connected the insulated disc of the absolute electrometer with the insulated ball A, thus substituting the disc wire and ball for the second system of conductors. A charge was communicated to the substituted system sufficient to attract upwards the aluminium square of the balance ; and the reading of the wire-image watched until from a slow escape of the charge along the insulating stems of the absolute electrometer, the attraction was just insufficient to keep the square in its sighted position. This method was found to give more consistent readings than when the insulating stems of the absolute electrometer were dried, and a coincidence obtained by moving the guard plate up or down. The observations on one of the days are given in Table XXVIII. The equation, by means of which the coefficient was deduced from the given data, is

$$V' - V = (D' - D) \sqrt{\frac{8\pi F}{A}}.$$

The mean of eight independent determinations shows the potential required to pass a spark between the discs when at a distance of $\cdot 5$ centimetre, and separated by air at atmospheric pressure to be 38·63 C.G.S. units.

The method above described has enabled me to investigate several of the laws of the disruptive discharge of electricity.

[*Added January 1878.*—In the tables appended we have entered almost all

the observations made. The mode of treating the observations was as follows:—I plotted the arguments and entries of each series of observations on section paper, and drew the curve which best satisfied these points of observation. After comparing all the curves so obtained, which related to one question, I found an equation,

$$y' = f(x),$$

which satisfied a curve to a first approximation, and calculated out the values of y' for all the points of observation; then since

$$y = y' \phi(x),$$

where y denotes the most probable observed value,

$$\phi(x) = \frac{y}{y'},$$

$\phi(x)$ was obtained by plotting $\frac{y}{y'}$ on an enlarged scale, drawing a curve by the graphic method, and finding an equation for that curve.]

Measurement of the Difference of Potential required to pass a Spark through Air at the Atmospheric Pressure between Parallel Metal Plates at Different Distances.

This problem has been investigated for small distances by Sir WILLIAM THOMSON; and it was from a perusal of his paper on the subject, in "Papers on Electrostatics and Magnetism," and the discussion of these results in CLERK MAXWELL'S "Electricity," that I was led to take the above subject for an experimental inquiry. Tables III., IV., V., VI., VII., VIII., and figs. 1, 2, 3, give the observations and inferences on this problem. The large discs mentioned as forming the electrodes were each of brass, 4 inches diameter, well rounded at the edge, the one having its face flat, the other slightly convex. A spherometer, the side of the base of which is 2.5 inches, gave the height of the convex segment through its feet to be .05 centimetre. The convex face belonged to the lower electrode. The diameter of the cylindrical part of the receiver used is 19 centimetres. The constants were the same for the five curves (Tables III. to VII.), excepting that the pressure and the temperature may have been slightly different. The maximum deflection could always be observed with precision, and the differences in the values for the same length of spark were probably due in great part to the spark not always passing exactly in the axis of the discs. The zero was always read after the second system of conductors had been completely discharged, which was always done after reading the maximum deflection. The values in the column headed Mean Difference of Potential are not always the mean of the values in the preceding column; but when not such, they are values got by concluding from independent evidence that greater weight ought to be attached to some of the entries than to the others. The entries to which greater weight has been

attached are marked with a cross thus, $\times$. The 6th column gives the same quantity expressed in absolute measure, the 7th gives the value calculated from the equation at the top of the table, and the 8th gives the differences between the most probable observed value (column 6th) and the calculated value. The letter e denotes that the spark was observed to pass from the edge of the disc in a bent path, and not from the centre in a straight path. The series of readings was continued until the distance was reached at which the spark began to pass from the edge, but not further, as the spark then passes under new conditions. This distance was found to be 1 centimetre. In fig. 1 and in all the following figures the intersection of the cross marks the mean observed value, and the curve is drawn by means of the equation at the top of the table. The reading when the spark passed from the edge was invariably less than when central and straight.

The five equations agree well with one another. In the case of the first four the differences are negative at the beginning, but in the case of the fifth positive. The equation for the curve, Table VI., squared, is

$$V^2 = 3\cdot7142s^4 - 494\cdot68s^3 + 4348\cdot5s^2 + 889\cdot52s,$$

where V denotes the difference of potential of the discs, and s the length of the spark.

Here the terms involving s^4 and s^3 are small compared with the terms involving s^2 and s , so long as s is not greater than 1 centimetre, the distance at which the spark begins to pass from the edge. Their existence is therefore probably due to the want of infiniteness in the diameter of the discs compared with the greater lengths of spark. By neglecting these higher terms we get the following results:—

Table.	Function for V .	a .	b .
III.	$66\cdot687 \sqrt{\{s^2 + \cdot20393s\}}$	$\cdot10196$	$6\cdot8000$
IV.	$66\cdot510 \sqrt{\{s^2 + \cdot20305s\}}$	$\cdot10152$	$6\cdot7523$
V.	$67\cdot337 \sqrt{\{s^2 + \cdot20351s\}}$	$\cdot10175$	$6\cdot8520$
VI.	$65\cdot945 \sqrt{\{s^2 + \cdot20455s\}}$	$\cdot10227$	$6\cdot7445$
VII.	$68\cdot167 \sqrt{\{s^2 + \cdot21015s\}}$	$\cdot10507$	$7\cdot1627$
Mean,	$66\cdot940 \sqrt{\{s^2 + \cdot20503s\}}$	$\cdot10251$	$6\cdot8623$

Here a and b are the semi-axes of the hyperbola represented by the equation; a meaning the number of centimetres which must be supposed added to the length of spark to make the difference of potential proportional to the length of the spark, and b the amount of difference of potential due to such a distance. The values for a , being independent of the absolute value of the entries, afford

a test of the accuracy of the experiments. The mean equation,

$$V = 66\cdot940 \sqrt{\{s^2 + \cdot20503s\}},$$

is drawn on fig. 1, so that it may be compared with the equation which passes through the points of observation. Assuming, then, that the above mean equation is true when the discs are of infinite extent, the equation for the electrostatic force is

$$R = 66\cdot940 \sqrt{\{1 + \cdot20503\frac{1}{s}\}},$$

where R denotes the electrostatic force, and s the length of the spark.

The values of R for several values of s are given in Table VIII., and the curve is drawn in fig. 2. Plotted along with it are several values for R , published by Sir WILLIAM THOMSON, p. 252 of "Papers." His measurements do not extend beyond 1·5 centimetre; the parts in common agree very well. From his observations, he concluded that the limiting value of R was something not much less than 130; the above equation gives 66·94.

According to the mathematical theory of electricity, if the conductors are in the form of two infinite parallel plates, then R is constant. The above function would give R constant were it not for the term involving s ; in the above example 889·52s. It is probable, then, that there is a physical condition which the mathematical theorem in question assumes implicitly, but which is not fulfilled in the conditions of the experiment. Professor CLERK MAXWELL says with reference to this (p. 56 of "Electricity and Magnetism")—

"It is difficult to explain why a thin stratum of air should require a greater force to produce a disruptive discharge across it than a thicker stratum. Is it possible that the air very near to the surface of dense bodies is condensed, so as to become a better insulator? or does the potential of an electrified conductor differ from that of the air in contact with it by a quantity having a maximum value just before discharge, so that the observed difference of potential of the conductors is in every case greater than the difference of potentials on the two sides of the stratum of air by a constant quantity, equivalent to the addition of about ·005 of an inch to the thickness of the stratum?"

Several of the series of observations in the succeeding tables were made to decide between these two hypotheses; the results fully establish, in my judgment, the former. The quantity (·005 inch, that is, ·0127 centimetre) is considerably less than the quantity above denoted by a . But if the two curves for R , fig. 2, are similar, the equation for Sir WILLIAM THOMSON'S curve is

$$R = 93\cdot322 \sqrt{\{1 + \frac{\cdot073718}{s}\}},$$

an equation satisfying well the given values, and according to it the value of a is ·037 centimetre.

The observations recorded in Table IX. were made with discs of much

smaller diameter—1·5 inch. The value of a , which is ·28433 centimetre, is greater than the value obtained with the large discs. But observations with the small discs have not been made for as many lengths of spark as is desirable.

Table X. gives the results for the same conditions as in Tables III. to VII., excepting that the density of the air is much less. The equation obtained by neglecting the higher powers of s is

$$V = 18\cdot292 \sqrt{\{s^2 + \cdot52322s\}},$$

which gives $a = \cdot26161$, and $b = 4\cdot7854$. Thus a is increased and b decreased. This leads us to infer that when the pressure is diminished the condensed stratum is also diminished—a conclusion which is supported by a peculiarity in Table XXIII., where, while the mean value for air before any exhaustion has been made is 152, the mean value after exhaustion thrice given is 142. a has always been found to be greater the smaller the pressure. The distance at which the spark was first observed to pass from the edge was 1·65 centimetre, compared with 1 centimetre for the ordinary pressure.

Table XI. (fig. 4) gives the results obtained when hydrogen was substituted for air. To effect this substitution I heated the brass discs thoroughly before the fire; then having screwed them on, I exhausted the air and let in hydrogen, repeating this process twice; but before taking any readings I left the hydrogen in for twenty-four hours. The curve through the readings is precisely similar to that for air, and the spark began to pass from the edge at very nearly the same distance. The equation obtained by neglecting the higher powers of s is

$$V = 43\cdot190 \sqrt{\{s^2 + \cdot13690s\}},$$

giving a to be ·06845 centimetre. The ratio of the intercepts for hydrogen and for air is thus ·66, which is not very different from the ratio of their electric strengths*—·63 given in column 6th of Table XXIII.—and agrees exactly with the value given in column 7th. I made only one determination of the absolute value of the difference of potential required to give a spark through hydrogen under the standard conditions. The value obtained, 12·1, is very nearly half of that obtained from the value for air by means of the ratio of the electric strengths of the two gases. I have provisionally taken the latter value. The necessity for leaving the hydrogen in for a length of time before taking the readings becomes manifest when the above table is compared with Table XII., which gives the results when the observations were taken immediately after the gas was put in. The observations are plotted on fig. 10. The curve given by the equation

$$V = 53\cdot940s - 12\cdot9316s^2,$$

which represents a parabola, runs well through all the observed values. There

* We have the high authority of Professor CLERK MAXWELL for using the term the electric strength of the gases to denote what has sometimes less properly been called their insulating power.

is then no term independent of s ; and the coefficient of s , it may be observed, is somewhat greater than the $\frac{b}{a}$ of the equation

$$V = 43.190 \sqrt{\{s^2 + .13690s\}}.$$

It thus appears that by heating the discs the cause of the existence of the term independent of s has been removed. Now, heating the discs removes condensed gas. The curvature involved in the parabola must be due to a decrease of temperature, as also to the increase of distance between the discs.

Table XIV. (fig. 12) contains the investigation for air under the same conditions. The results are precisely similar. The ratio of the coefficients of the equation for hydrogen is 4.17, while that of the coefficients of the equation for air is 4.45. The coefficient of s is somewhat greater than the $\frac{b}{a}$ of the equation

$$V = 66.940 \sqrt{\{s^2 + .20503s\}}.$$

Their ratio is 1.30, while for hydrogen the ratio is 1.25. The investigation of Table XIII. (fig. 11) is the same as that of Table XIV., excepting that in heating the discs the air inside the receiver was also heated; whereas, in the case of Table XIV., only the discs were heated, a difference, in my opinion, sufficient to account for the difference in the magnitude of the coefficients. During this series of observations special notice was taken of the place where the spark passed. c denotes that it was at the centre, and nc that it was near the centre.

In Table XV. are observations undertaken to test whether a change in the capacity of the charged conductor has any effect upon the readings. The couple of small Leyden jars referred to are those usually hung on the conductors of the Holtz; they were always on when measurements were made, excepting in the case of Table XVIII. The capacity of the large jar when tested was found to be five times that of the couple of small jars. If the three last readings for the large jars are more correct than their predecessors, it would appear that the change of capacity has no effect upon the reading. But the difference of the curves of Tables XVII. and XVIII., if not otherwise explicable, supports the opposite conclusion.

Table XVI.—By “continued discharge,” is meant a discharge which kept the spot of light at a fixed deflection. This deflection was always less than that for the corresponding single discharge. The image can be made to remain very steady with only a slight oscillation. The zero was more displaced than in the case of the single spark, owing probably to the greater

amount of electrification introduced inside the electrometer. Between the fifth and sixth observations the apparatus was disturbed, which accounts for the larger differences. The observations of this table, taken together with those of Table XX., show that the curves for the continued discharge are similar to those for the single, but are of smaller magnitude.

Measurement of the Difference of Potential required to produce the same length of Spark at different pressures of the Dielectric.

In this independent variation we have not the complexity introduced by a change of distance between the electrodes. We accordingly have simpler equations; the simple hyperbola satisfies well all the points of observation.

The observations of Tables XVII. and XVIII. were taken in immediate succession. The latter give very accurately an hyperbola, the former require a small correction. I think that the latter curve was taken under more favourable auspices as regards the state of the observers; the readings in themselves were more difficult to take, on account of the slow velocity with which it was necessary to drive the machine owing to the small capacity of the conductor. The observations of Tables XIX. and XX. also give hyperbolas. The results are,—

Table.	Function for V.	<i>a.</i>	<i>b.</i>
XVII.	$\cdot04798 \sqrt{\{p^2 + 205\cdot58p\}}$	102·79	4·6678
XVIII.	$\cdot044551 \sqrt{\{p^2 + 200p\}}$	100	4·4551
XIX.	$\cdot046342 \sqrt{\{p^2 + 199\cdot01p\}}$	99·51	4·6112
XX.	$\cdot046853 \sqrt{\{p^2 + 207\cdot06p\}}$	103·53	4·8508
Mean	$\cdot045794 \sqrt{\{p^2 + 202\cdot92p\}}$	101·46	4·6462

where *a* and *b* denote the semi-axes of the hyperbola, and *p* the pressure in millimetres of mercury. $\frac{b}{a}$ for XVIII., which is the curve obtained without Leyden jars, is smaller than for any other of the curves.

The observations for the continued discharge, Table XX., were taken each after the reading for the corresponding single discharge. By neglecting the higher terms of *p*, we get

$$V = \cdot035032 \sqrt{\{p^2 + 205\cdot62p\}},$$

where V denotes the difference of potential of the discs, and p the pressure of the dielectric; which gives $a=102\cdot81$ compared with $103\cdot53$ for the single spark; and $b=3\cdot6016$ compared with $4\cdot8508$. The two curves are represented together on fig. 13.

Table XXI. contains an investigation of the same problem with this difference, that the length of spark was 1 centimetre, whereas in all the preceding series of observations it was $\cdot5$ centimetre. The equation is similar. The ratio of the $\frac{b}{a}$ of the $\cdot5$ centimetre curve to that of the 1 centimetre curve ought to be $\frac{38\cdot878}{70\cdot207}$, that is $\cdot554$. The mean equation and the equation of this table give $\cdot568$.

I regret that I did not take a series of observations in the reverse order, for it may be that the exhausting of the air before taking the observations took away the condensed air in great part. The curve for hydrogen instead of air (Table XXII. fig. 6) happened to be investigated in the reverse order. The mean points lie very accurately on an hyperbola, excepting that for 262, where there may have been an error in reading the number. The equation

$$V = \cdot012 \sqrt{\{p^2 + 600p\}}$$

gives $a=300$, and $b=3\cdot600$. The largeness of the a compared with that for air affords an additional ground for inferring that the order of procedure is not indifferent.

The Electric Strength of Different Gases.

Table XXIII.—The first values for air were taken before any exhaustion was made; and each of the observed differences of potential, with the exception of the second, the smallness of which is probably due to a mistake of 10 in reading, is decidedly greater than any afterwards observed for air. The less value of the subsequent readings for air must have been due to the exhaustions involved in the change of gas, which were always to 3 mm. or so. It does not seem due to any change of sensitiveness in the electrometer; for then there would have been a falling off in the third and fourth mean values. Hence 142 has been chosen, and not 152, as the proper reading for air, and the values given in column 6th are deduced from 142. Column 7th contains the mean of all other determinations made of the relative electric strength; and these means agree pretty closely with the values of column 6th. Column 8th contains FARADAY'S values. (Section 1388 of "Experimental Researches in Electricity.") These numbers all agree in being less than the corresponding number in column 6th; but this is explained by the fact that FARADAY'S num-

ber is the ratio of the thicknesses of the insulators when they are equally strong, not the ratio of the strengths of the insulators when they are equally thick. The one ratio is not equal to the other, unless the function connecting the difference of potential with the length of spark is that of the straight line ; which was not the case under the conditions of his measurements.

Measurement of the Difference of Potential required to pass a Spark between two Spherical Balls at Different Distances.

Tables XXIV. to XXVII., and figs. 14 and 15.—The balls used as electrodes were each 1 inch in diameter, and when in use were screwed on to the rods. Observations were taken through a much greater range of distances than when the electrodes were discs, because no discontinuity was observed such as took place with the discs. I have not expressed the results in absolute measure in the tables, because the observations necessary for the immediate comparison were not taken, and also because there is need of another series of observations taken with the improvements in the apparatus introduced after these observations were made to decide definitely between various hypotheses which they suggest. In the case of Table XXIV., fig. 15, the equation was chosen to satisfy the observations between .5 and 8, which it does very well ; but it does not satisfy the rest of the observations. There certainly is a discontinuity in the observations, which was due to the commencement of an escape from the insulated wire. The four series of observations agree in giving the same kind of function for V. By making some assumptions the equations have been reduced to absolute measure, so that the relative magnitudes at least are correct.

Table.	Pressure.	Function for V.	Value of s for Maximum.
XXIV.	85	$10.442s^{\frac{1}{2}} - .36907s^{\frac{3}{2}}$	9.65
XXV.	40	$6.8477s^{\frac{1}{2}} - .26015s^{\frac{3}{2}}$	8.77
XXVI.	20	$4.5069s^{\frac{1}{2}} - .10043s^{\frac{3}{2}}$	14.96
XXVII.	30	$5.7920s^{\frac{1}{2}} - .17822s^{\frac{3}{2}}$	10.83

The values of s for a maximum coincide pretty closely with the values of s, at which the escape begins. This is seen well in fig. 15, where all the observed values up to the maximum lie well on the curve given by the function ; one

only is slightly out. These results confirm the conclusion that we inferred from our preliminary experiments of the summer of 1876, that the curve is to a first approximation a parabola.

In conclusion, our thanks are due to the Professor of Natural Philosophy for bearing the expense of what was new in the arrangement, and to the Professor of Chemistry for the loan of apparatus for the preparation of the gases.

TABLE I.—Induction Curve, 29th May 1877. Electrodes, balls. Pressure, 160 mm. Length of Spark, 6 centimetres.

Equ. I. $V = 4522 \cdot 6r^{-1} - 20 \cdot 24$. Equ. II. $V = 2903 \cdot 5r^{-1} + 58 \cdot 073 - \cdot 31807r$.

Distance between Centres of Balls. <i>r</i> Centimetres.	Deflection. <i>n</i> .	Zero. <i>n</i> ⁰ .	Observed Difference of Potential. <i>n</i> ¹ - <i>n</i> .	Mean Difference of Potential. <i>V</i> ¹ .	Calculated Difference of Potential Equ. I. <i>V</i> .	Calculated Difference of Potential Equ. II. <i>V</i> .
14·5	230	484	254	253·7	291·66	253·70
	230		254			
	231		253			
15·5	248	"	236	238	271·54	240·47
	240		244			
	250		238			
16·5	254	"	230	229·3	253·86	228·79
	254		230			
	256		228			
17·5	270	"	214	219	233·19	218·42
	265		219 ×			
	265		219			
18·5	280	"	204	212	224·22	209·14
	270		214			
	267		217			
19·5	275	"	209	204	211·69	200·77
	280		204 ×			
	280		204			
20·5	290	"	194 ×	194	200·37	193·19
	285		199			
	284		200			
21·5	297	"	187 ×	187	190·11	186·28
	293		191			
	297		187			
22·5	306	"	178	178	180·76	179·96
	306		178			
	307		177			
23·5	310	"	174	172	172·21	174·15
	314		170			
	313		171			
24·5	318	"	166	161·3	164·36	...
	325		159			
	325		159			

TABLE I.—*continued.*

Distance between Centres of Balls. <i>r</i> Centimetres.	Deflection. <i>n</i> .	Zero. <i>n</i> ¹ .	Observed Difference of Potential. <i>n</i> ¹ - <i>n</i> .	Mean Difference of Potential. $\frac{1}{2} V^1$.	Calculated Difference of Potential Equ. I. V.	Calculated Difference of Potential Equ. II. V.
25.5	334	484	150	155	157.11	...
	328		156			
	325		159			
27.5	335	"	149	144	144.22	...
	340		144 ×			
	340		144			
29.5	350	"	134	132	133.07	...
	352		132			
	354		130			
31.5	362	"	122	122.7	123.33	...
	360		124			
	362		122			
33.5	369	"	115	114	114.76	...
	370		114			
	372		112			
35.5	377	"	107	108	107.16	...
	375		109			
	376		108			
37.5	382	"	102 ×	102	100.36	...
	381		103			
	381		103			
39.5	392	"	92	93.3	94.25	...
	390		94			
	390		94			
41.5	399	"	85	88.7	88.74	...
	394		90			
	393		91			
43.5	399	"	85	84.7	83.73	...
	400		84			
	399		85			
48.0	410	"	74	74.7	73.98	...
	410		74			
	408		76			

TABLE II.—Induction Curve, 20th July 1877. Electrodes, large discs. Pressure, 740 mm. Length of Spark, .5 centimetres.

Equ. I. $V = 6081.7r^{-1} - 42.262$. Equ. II. $V = 3188.4r^{-1} + 98.32 - .83970r$.

Distance between Centres of Balls in Centimetres. <i>r</i> .	Deflection. <i>n</i> .	Zero. <i>n</i> ¹ .	Observed Difference of Potential. <i>n</i> ¹ - <i>n</i> .	Calculated Difference of Potential Equ. I. V.	Calculated Difference of Potential Equ. II. V.
12.75	185	523	338	434.74	337.68
15.25	227	"	296	356.54	294.59
17.75	263	"	260	300.38	263.05
20.25	283	"	240	258.07	238.77

TABLE II.—*continued.*

Distance between Centres of Balls in Centimetres. <i>r.</i>	Deflection. <i>n.</i>	Zero. <i>n</i> ¹ .	Observed Difference of Potential. <i>n</i> ¹ - <i>n.</i>	Calculated Difference of Potential Equ. I. V.	Calculated Difference of Potential Equ. II. V.
22.75	305	523	218	224.45	219.00
25.25	328	526	198	199.15	203.39
27.75	347	523	176	176.90	189.92
30.25	363	"	160	158.79	...
32.75	380	"	143	143.44	...
35.25	393	"	130	130.27	...
37.75	405	525	120	118.85	...
40.25	417	"	108	108.84	...
42.75	428	"	97	100.00	...
45.25	436	"	89	92.14	...
47.75	440	"	85	82.21	...
50.25	444	"	81	78.77	...
52.75	450	"	75	73.03	...
55.25	456	"	69	67.82	...
57.75	462	"	63	63.05	...
60.25	464	524	60	58.68	...
62.75	470	"	54	54.66	...

TABLE III.—Distance Curve, 15th June 1877. Electrodes, large discs. Pressure, atmospheric.

$$\text{Equation, } V = (67.340 - 3.2500s) \sqrt{\{s^2 + .2s\}}.$$

Length of Spark in Centimetres. <i>s.</i>	Deflection. <i>n.</i>	Zero. <i>n</i> ¹ .	Observed Diff. of Potential. <i>n</i> ¹ - <i>n.</i>	Mean Diff. of Potential.	Mean Diff. of Potential in absolute measure. <i>v</i> ¹ .	Calculated Value in absolute measure. V.	Difference. <i>V</i> ¹ - V.
.05	473	500	27	27.3	7.479	7.512	-0.033
	475	"	27				
	476	504	28				
.1	463	505	42	42.3	11.589	11.608	-0.019
	463	"	42				
	462	"	43				
.2	436	"	69	68	18.630	18.862	-0.232
	435	"	70				
	440	"	65				
.3	408	"	97	93.3	25.561	25.702	-0.141
	415	507	92				
	418	509	91				
.4	388	"	121	120	32.876	32.352	+0.524
	390	510	120 ×				
	391	511	120				
.5	373	513	140	142.7	39.095	38.878	+0.217
	370	"	143				
	365	510	145				

TABLE III.—*continued.*

Length of Spark in Centimetres. <i>s.</i>	Deflection. <i>n.</i>	Zero. <i>n</i> ¹ .	Observed Diff. of Potential. <i>n</i> ¹ - <i>n.</i>	Mean Diff. of Potential.	Mean Diff. of Potential in absolute measure. <i>V</i> ¹ .	Calculated Value in absolute measure. <i>V.</i>	Difference. <i>V</i> ¹ - <i>V.</i>	
·6	{	350	515	165	} 164	44·931	45·304	-0·373
		354	514	160				
		350	517	167				
·7	{	330	„	187	} 189	51·780	51·640	+0·140
		330	523	193				
		330	516	186				
·8	{	310	522	212	} 211	57·807	57·904	-0·097
		312	523	211				
		315	525	210				
·9	{	300	523	223	} 227	62·192	64·091	-1·899
		308	525	217				
		303	530	227 ×				
1·0	{	283	533	250	} 249·3	68·300	70·207	-1·907
		286	536	250				
		290	538	248				

TABLE IV.—Distance Curve, 9th July 1877. Electrodes, large discs. Pressure, 750 mm. Temperature, 73° Fahrenheit.

$$\text{Equation, } V = (67\cdot015 - 2\cdot5142s) \sqrt{\{s^2 + \cdot2s\}}.$$

Length of Spark in Centimetres. <i>s.</i>	Deflection. <i>n.</i>	Zero. <i>n</i> ¹ .	Observed Diff. of Potential. <i>n</i> ¹ - <i>n.</i>	Mean Diff. of Potential.	Mean Diff. of Potential in absolute measure. <i>V</i> ¹ .	Calculated Value in absolute measure. <i>V.</i>	Difference. <i>V</i> ¹ - <i>V.</i>	
·025	{	502	512	10	} 10	3·75	5·02	-1·27
		502	„	10				
		502	„	10				
·05	{	495	„	17	} 18	6·75	7·48	-0·73
		493	„	19				
		494	„	18				
·075	{	488	„	24	} 24	9·00	9·60	-0·60
		488	„	24				
		488	„	24				
·1	{	479	„	33 ×	} 33	12·37	11·56	+0·81
		479	„	33				
		478	„	34				
·15	{	470	„	42	} 42	15·75	15·27	+0·48
		470	„	42				
		470	„	42				
·2	{	462	„	50	} 51·7	19·39	18·81	+0·58
		460	„	52				
		459	„	53				
·25	{	448	„	64	} 63	23·62	22·27	+1·35
		448	„	64				
		451	„	61				

TABLE IV.—*continued.*

Length of Spark in Centimetres. <i>s.</i>	Deflection. <i>n.</i>	Zero. <i>n</i> ¹ .	Observed Diff. of Potential. <i>n</i> ¹ - <i>n.</i>	Mean Diff. of Potential.	Mean Diff. of Potential in absolute measure. <i>v</i> ¹ .	Calculated Value in absolute measure. <i>v.</i>	Difference. <i>v</i> ¹ - <i>v.</i>
·3	436	512	76	74	27·75	25·66	+2·09
	438	"	74 ×				
	434	"	78				
·35	430	514	84	79	29·63	29·02	+0·61
	430	"	84				
	435	"	79 ×				
·4	428	"	86	86	32·25	32·34	-0·09
	430	516	86				
	430	"	86				
·45	422	"	94	95	35·62	35·63	-0·01
	421	"	95				
	421	"	95				
·5	410	"	106	105	39·38	38·90	+0·48
	412	518	106				
	415	"	103				
·6	408	"	110	118	44·25	45·38	-1·13
	400	"	118 ×				
	400	"	118				
·7	378	517	139	138·3	51·87	51·80	+0·07
	378	"	139				
	380	"	137				
·8	367	"	150	154·7	58·02	58·14	-0·12
	366	520	154				
	365	525	160				
·9	357	528	171	172	64·50	64·43	+0·07
	355	525	170				
	350	"	175				
1·0	e 332	510	178	179·3	67·25	70·66	-3·41
	e 330	515	185				
	e 340	"	175				

TABLE V.—Distance Curve, 14th June 1877. Electrodes, large discs. Pressure, atmospheric. Temperature, 74° Fahrenheit. Equation, $V = \{67·925 - 2·9303s\} \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(s^2 + \cdot 2s)}$.

Length of Spark in Centimetres. <i>s.</i>	Deflection. <i>n.</i>	Zero. <i>n</i> ¹ .	Observed Diff. of Potential. <i>n</i> ¹ - <i>n.</i>	Mean Diff. of Potential.	Mean Diff. of Potential in absolute measure. <i>v</i> ¹ .	Calculated Diff. of Potential in abs. meas. <i>v.</i>	Difference. <i>v</i> ¹ - <i>v.</i>
·05	480	510	30	30	5·88	7·58	-1·70
	480	"	30				
	480	"	30				
·1	450	505	55 ×	55	10·78	11·71	-0·93
	452	"	53				
	452	"	53				
·2	415	"	90	90	17·65	19·05	-1·40
	415	"	90				
	415	"	90				

TABLE V.—*continued.*

Length of Spark in Centimetres. <i>s.</i>	Deflection. <i>n.</i>	Zero. <i>n</i> ¹ .	Observed Diff. of Potential. <i>n</i> ¹ - <i>n.</i>	Mean Diff. of Potential.	Mean Diff. of Potential in absolute measure. <i>V</i> ¹ .	Calculated Diff. of Potential in abs. meas. <i>V.</i>	Difference. <i>V</i> ¹ - <i>V.</i>	
·3	{	377	510	133	} 134	26·27	25·97	+0·30
		390	512	122				
		380	515	135				
·4	{	350	522	172	} 167	32·74	32·70	+0·04
		337	503	166				
		347	510	163				
·5	{	313	512	199	} 199·3	39·08	39·33	-0·25
		313	512	199				
		316	516	200				
·6	{	288	520	232	} 234	45·88	45·84	+0·04
		288	523	235				
		290	525	235				
·7	{	257	527	270	} 269·3	52·81	52·29	+0·52
		260	530	270				
		265	533	268				
·8	{	255	540	285	} 296·5	58·14	58·66	-0·52
		245	545	300 ×				
		255	548	293 ×				
·9	{	233	552	319	} 323	63·34	64·96	-1·62
		240	557	317				
		235	568	333				
1·0	{	215	573	358	} 363	71·18	71·20	-0·02
		212	578	366				
1·1	{	215	580	365	394	77·26	77·37	-0·11
		<i>e</i> 186	„	394				

TABLE VI.—Distance Curve, 17th July 1877. Electrodes, large discs.
Pressure, 737 mm.

$$\text{Equation } V = \{66\cdot69 - 3\cdot7142s\} \sqrt{\{s^2 + \cdot2s\}}.$$

Length of Spark in Centimetres. <i>s.</i>	Deflection. <i>n.</i>	Zero. <i>n</i> ¹ .	Observed Diff. of Potential. <i>n</i> ¹ - <i>n.</i>	Mean Diff. of Potential.	Mean Diff. of Potential in absolute measure. <i>V</i> ¹ .	Calculated Diff. of Potential in abs. meas. <i>V.</i>	Difference. <i>V</i> ¹ - <i>V.</i>	
·06	{	479	508	29	} 29	8·24	8·32	-0·08
		480	509	29				
·11	{	466	510	44	} 43·5	12·35	12·24	+0·11
		467	„	43				
·21	{	441	„	69	} 68	19·31	19·34	-0·03
		443	„	67				
·31	{	415	512	97	} 96	27·27	26·06	+1·21
		418	513	95				
·41	{	400	„	113	} 112·5	31·95	32·59	-0·64
		398	510	112				
·51	{	370	„	140	} 138	39·19	38·99	+0·20
		374	„	136				

TABLE VI.—*continued.*

Length of Spark in Centimetres. <i>s.</i>	Deflection. <i>n.</i>	Zero. <i>n</i> ¹ .	Observed Diff. of Potential. <i>n</i> ² - <i>n.</i>	Mean Diff. of Potential.	Mean Diff. of Potential in absolute measure. <i>V</i> ¹ .	Calculated Diff. of Potential in abs. meas. <i>V.</i>	Difference. <i>V</i> ¹ - <i>V.</i>
·61	352	510	158	} 156	44·31	45·29	-0·98
	358	512	154				
·71	327	"	185	} 183·5	52·12	51·49	+0·63
	330	"	182				
·81	310	"	202 ×	} 202	57·37	57·60	-0·23
	320	517	197				

TABLE VII.—Distance Curve, 13th June 1877. Electrodes, large discs. Pressure, atmospheric. Equation $V = (69·875 - 8·9375s)\sqrt{\{s^2 + \cdot2s\}}$.

Length of Spark in Centimetres. <i>s.</i>	Deflection. <i>n.</i>	Zero. <i>n</i> ¹ .	Observed Diff. of Potential. <i>n</i> ² - <i>n.</i>	Mean Diff. of Potential.	Mean Diff. of Potential in absolute measure. <i>V</i> ¹ .	Calculated Value in absolute measure. <i>V.</i>	Difference. <i>V</i> ¹ - <i>V.</i>
·1	460	505	45 ×	} 45	13·37	11·95	+1·42
	458	"	47				
·2	460	"	45	} 67	19·91	19·26	+0·65
	437	"	68				
·3	438	"	67 ×	} 89	26·45	26·02	+0·43
	438	"	67				
·4	415	"	90	} 105	31·20	32·48	-1·28
	418	"	87				
·5	414	"	91	} 132	39·22	38·69	+0·35
	403	"	102				
·6	400	"	105 ×	} 150	44·58	44·69	-0·11
	402	"	103				
·7	370	"	135	} 173	51·41	50·50	+0·91
	375	"	130				
·8	375	"	130	} 189	56·16	56·10	+0·06
	354	"	151				
·9	356	"	149	} 207·3	61·60	61·52	+0·08
	355	"	150				
1·0	334	"	171	} 226	67·16	66·75	+0·41
	330	"	175				
1·1	332	"	173	} 239	71·02	71·80	-0·78
	318	"	187				
	314	"	191	} 226	67·16	66·75	+0·41
	315	"	190				
	297	"	208	} 239	71·02	71·80	-0·78
	296	"	209				
	300	"	205	} 226	67·16	66·75	+0·41
	280	"	225				
	280	"	225	} 239	71·02	71·80	-0·78
	276	"	229				
	e268	"	237	} 239	71·02	71·80	-0·78
	e265	"	240				
	e265	"	240				

TABLE VIII.—Deduced Curves.

Difference of Potential Curve, $V = 66.940 \sqrt{\{s^2 + .20503s\}}$.

Electrostatic Force Curve, $R = 66.940 \sqrt{\left\{1 + \frac{.20503}{s}\right\}}$.

Pressure Curve, $p = .18168 \left\{1 + \frac{.20503}{s}\right\}$.

Length of Spark in Centimetres. <i>s</i> .	Difference of Potential in C. G. S. units. <i>V</i> .	Electrostatic Force. $R = \frac{V}{s}$.	Pressure. $p = \frac{R^2}{8\pi \times 981 \cdot 4}$.
.025	5.076	203.05	1.3470
.05	7.559	151.18	.9267
.075	9.701	129.35	.6783
.1	11.691	116.91	.5542
.2	19.052	95.26	.3679
.3	26.056	86.85	.3058
.4	32.932	82.33	.2748
.5	39.745	79.49	.2562
.6	46.524	77.54	.2437
.7	53.281	76.11	.2349
.8	60.024	75.03	.2282
.9	66.756	74.17	.2231
1.0	73.484	73.48	.2189

TABLE IX.—Distance Curves, 4th June 1877. Electrodes, small discs. Pressure, atmospheric.

Equation, $V = 52.840 \sqrt{\{s^2 + .56866s\}}$.

Length of Spark in Centimetres. <i>s</i> .	Deflection. <i>n</i> .	Zero. <i>n</i> ¹ .	Observed Diff. of Potential. <i>n</i> ¹ - <i>n</i> .	Mean Diff. of Potential.	Mean Diff. of Potential in absolute measure. <i>V</i> ¹ .	Calculated Diff. of Potential. <i>V</i> .	Difference. <i>V</i> ¹ - <i>V</i> .
.25	468	498.5	30.5	28.5	24.74	23.91	+0.83
	470	"	28.5 ×				
	470	"	28.5				
.5	470	"	28.5	44.5	38.63	38.63	0.00
	454	"	44.5				
	454	"	44.5				
.75	454	"	44.5	60.75	52.74	52.56	+0.18
	436	"	62.5				
	438	"	60.5				
1.0	437	"	61.5	76.25	66.19	66.19	0.00
	440	"	58.5				
	423	"	75.5				
1.25	422	"	76.5	89.2	77.43	79.67	-2.24
	421	"	77.5				
	e410	"	88.5				
	e410	"	88.5				
	e408	"	90.5				

TABLE IX.—*continued.*

Electrodes, small discs. Pressure, 180 mm.

Equation, $V = 6.0767 \sqrt{\{s^2 + 15.040s\}}$.

Length of Spark in Centimetres. <i>s.</i>	Deflection. <i>n.</i>	Zero. <i>n</i> ¹ .	Observed Diff. of Potential. <i>n</i> ¹ - <i>n.</i>	Mean Diff. of Potential.	Mean Diff. of Potential in absolute measure. <i>v</i> ¹ .	Calculated Diff. of Potential. <i>V.</i>	Difference. <i>V</i> ¹ - <i>V.</i>
.25	482	498.5	16.5	14	12.15	11.88	+0.27
	485	"	13.5				
	485	"	13.5				
	486	"	12.5				
.5	476	"	22.5	19.5	16.93	16.94	-0.01
	480	"	18.5				
	479	"	19.5				
	480	"	18.5				
	480	"	18.5				
.75	475	"	23.5	25.1	21.79	20.91	+0.88
	472	"	26.5				
	472	"	26.5				
	473	"	25.5				
	475	"	23.5				
1.0	472	"	26.5	27.1	23.53	24.34	-0.81
	471	"	27.5				
	470	"	28.5				
	474	"	24.5				
	470	"	28.5				
1.25	462	"	36.5	33.3	28.91	27.42	+1.49
	466	"	32.5				
	465	"	33.5				
	466	"	32.5				
	467	"	31.5				
1.5	462	"	36.5	35.9	31.16	30.27	+0.89
	461	"	37.5				
	463	"	35.5				
	465	"	33.5				
	462	"	36.5				

TABLE X.—Distance Curve, 6th June 1877. Electrodes, large discs.
Pressure, 180 mm.

Equation, $V = (19.724 - 3.0666s) \sqrt{\{s^2 + .45s\}}$.

Length of Spark in Centimetres. s.	Deflection. n.	Zero. n ¹ .	Observed Diff. of Potential. n ¹ - n.	Mean Diff. of Potential.	Mean Diff. of Potential in absolute measure. V ¹ .	Calculated Diff. of Potential in abs. meas. V.	Difference. V ¹ - V.
.15	478	498	20	20	5.79	5.78	+0.01
	478		20				
	478		20				
.25	470	498	28 x	28	8.11	7.93	+0.18
	469		29				
	470		28				
.35	463	498	35	35	10.13	9.87	+0.26
	463		35				
	463		35				
.45	457	498	41	40	11.58	11.67	-0.09
	458		40				
	459		39				
.55	453	498	45	45	13.03	13.38	-0.35
	452		46				
	454		44				
.65	447	498	51	49.7	14.39	14.99	-0.60
	448		50				
	450		48				
.75	444	498	54	54.3	15.72	16.53	-0.81
	444		54				
	443		55				
.85	438	498	60	61.3	17.75	17.99	-0.24
	436		62				
	436		62				
.95	430	498	68	67	19.40	19.39	+0.01
	430		68				
	433		65				
1.05	427	498	71	71	20.56	20.71	-0.15
	426		72				
	428		70				
1.15	423	498	75	75.7	21.92	21.97	-0.05
	422		76				
	422		76				
1.25	419	498	79	80	23.16	23.16	0.00
	417		81				
	418		80				
1.35	413	498	85	85.3	24.69	24.29	+0.40
	413		85				
	412		86				
1.45	408	498	90	90.3	26.14	25.36	+0.78
	409		89				
	406		92				
1.55	403	498	95	94.7	27.42	26.36	+1.06
	403		95				
	404		94				
1.65	e						

TABLE XI.—Hydrogen Distance Curve, 12th July 1877. Dielectric, Hydrogen.
Electrodes, large discs. Pressure, 752 mm. Temperature, 70° Fahr.

$$\text{Equation, } V = (43.334 - 1.042s) \sqrt{\{s^2 + .136s\}}.$$

Length of Spark in Centimetres. <i>s.</i>	Deflection. <i>n.</i>	Zero. <i>n</i> ¹ .	Observed Diff. of Potential. <i>n</i> ¹ - <i>n.</i>	Mean Diff. of Potential.	Mean Diff. of Potential in absolute measure. <i>V</i> ¹ .	Calculated Diff. of Potential in abs. meas. <i>V.</i>	Difference. <i>V</i> ¹ - <i>V.</i>
.06	{ 498	510	12	} 12	3.99	4.69	-0.70
	{ 498	"	12				
.11	{ 492	"	18	} 18	5.99	7.11	-1.12
	{ 492	"	18				
.16	{ 482	"	28	} 28	9.32	9.39	-0.07
	{ 482	"	28				
.21	{ 474	"	36 ×	} 35	11.98	11.62	+0.36
	{ 473	"	37				
.26	{ 468	511	43	} 43	14.31	13.82	+0.49
	{ 469	512	43				
.31	{ 463	511	48	} 48	15.98	15.99	-0.01
	{ 462	510	48				
.41	{ 453	511	58	} 59	19.68	20.30	-0.62
	{ 452	"	59 ×				
.51	{ 439	"	72	} 72.5	24.12	24.57	-0.45
	{ 438	"	73				
.61	{ 423	"	88 ×	} 88	29.28	28.80	+0.48
	{ 423	512	89				
.71	{ 414	"	98	} 98.5	32.78	33.01	-0.23
	{ 413	"	99				
.81	{ 398	"	114	} 112	37.28	37.19	+0.09
	{ 403	"	109				
	{ 399	"	113				
.91	{ 388	"	124	} 124	41.26	41.35	-0.09
	{ 388	"	124				
1.01	{ 377	510	133 ×	} 136	45.26	45.49	-0.23
	{ 379	"	131				
	{ 376	514	138 ×				
1.11	{ 359	510	151	} 150	49.92	49.60	+0.32
	{ 361	"	149				
	{ 358	514	156				
1.21	{ 356	"	158	} 158.7	52.82	53.69	-0.87
	{ 363	512	149				
	{ 343	"	169				

TABLE XII.—Hydrogen Distance Curve, discs having first been heated. 11th July 1877. Dielectric, Hydrogen. Electrodes, large discs. Pressure, atmospheric.

$$\text{Equation, } V = 53.940s - 12.9316s^2.$$

Length of Spark in Centimetres. s.	Deflection. n.	Zero. n ¹ .	Observed Diff. of Potential. n ¹ -n.	Mean Diff. of Potential.	Mean Diff. of Potential in absolute measure. V ¹ .	Calculated Diff. of Potential in abs. meas. V.	Difference. V ¹ -V.
·02	{ 506 505 505	510 " "	{ 4 5 × 5	} 5	·95	1·07	-0·12
·07	{ 492 490 491	" " "	{ 18 20 × 19	} 20	3·80	3·71	+0·09
·12	{ 475 473	" "	{ 35 × 37	} 35	6·65	6·29	+0·36
·17	{ 463 461	" "	{ 47 × 49	} 47	8·93	8·80	+0·13
·22	{ 450 448	" "	{ 60 × 62	} 60	11·40	11·24	+0·16
·32	{ 426 425	" "	{ 84 85	} 84·5	16·06	15·94	+0·12
·42	{ 403 402	" "	{ 107 108	} 107·5	20·43	20·38	+0·05
·52	{ 383 385	" "	{ 127 × 125	} 127	24·13	24·55	-0·42
·62	{ 361 361	" "	{ 149 149	} 149	27·67	28·47	-0·80
·72	{ 345 343	" "	{ 165 167	} 166	31·55	32·13	-0·58
·82	{ 323 322	" "	{ 187 188	} 187·5	35·63	35·45	+0·18
·92	{ 306 310	" "	{ 204 × 200	} 204	38·77	38·68	+0·09
1·02	{ 290 288	" "	{ 220 222	} 221	41·99	41·57	+0·42
1·12	{ 293 290	" "	{ 217 × 220	} 217	41·52	41·03	+0·49

TABLE XIII.—Air Distance Curve, discs having first been heated, 13th July 1877. Dielectric, Air. Electrodes, large discs. Pressure, 742 mm. Temperature, 70° Fahr.

Equation, $V = 89.240s - 33.815s^2$.

Length of Spark in Centimetres. s.	Deflection. n.	Zero. n ¹ .	Observed Diff. of Potential. n ¹ - n.	Mean Diff. of Potential.	Mean Diff. of Potential in absolute measure. V ¹ .	Calculated Diff. of Potential in abs. meas. V.	Difference. V ¹ - V.																																																																																																																																																																																																																							
.035	508	512	4 ×	4	2.06	3.08	-1.02																																																																																																																																																																																																																							
	507	510	3					.06	500	"	10	10	5.15	5.23	-0.08	500	"	10	.085	495.5	"	14.5	14.5	7.47	7.34	+0.13	495.5	"	14.5	.11	489	"	21	21	10.82	9.41	+1.41	489	"	21	.16	483	509	26 ×	26	13.39	13.41	-0.02	482	507	25	.21	482	"	25	36	18.54	17.25	+1.29	470	506	36	.31	470	"	36	47.5	24.46	24.41	+0.05	459	"	47	.41	458	"	48	60	30.90	30.90	0.00	448	"	58	.51	446	508	62	69	35.54	36.71	-1.17	439	"	69	.61	440	509	69	81	41.72	41.86	-0.14	428	"	81	.71	428	"	81	88.7	45.69	46.31	-0.62	421	"	88	.81	419	"	90	98	50.48	50.10	+0.38	nc 421	"	88	.91	nc 412	"	97	103.3	53.21	53.21	0.00	c 410	"	99	1.01	c 405	"	104	106.3	54.75	55.38	-0.63	nc 404	"	105	1.11	c 408	"	101	111	57.17	57.40	-0.23	c 404	"	105	1.21	c 403	"	106	113.5	58.46	58.40	+0.06	c 402	510	108	1.31	c 400	512	112	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30	nc 402	"	110	1.41	c 393	"	119	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	c 396	511	115 ×	1.31	c 400	512	112 ×	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30	394	"	118	1.41	e 401	509	108	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	nc 397	"	115	1.41	e 396	508	112	111.7	57.69
.06	500	"	10	10	5.15	5.23	-0.08																																																																																																																																																																																																																							
	500	"	10					.085	495.5	"	14.5	14.5	7.47	7.34	+0.13	495.5	"	14.5	.11	489	"	21	21	10.82	9.41	+1.41	489	"	21	.16	483	509	26 ×	26	13.39	13.41	-0.02	482	507	25	.21	482	"	25	36	18.54	17.25	+1.29	470	506	36	.31	470	"	36	47.5	24.46	24.41	+0.05	459	"	47	.41	458	"	48	60	30.90	30.90	0.00	448	"	58	.51	446	508	62	69	35.54	36.71	-1.17	439	"	69	.61	440	509	69	81	41.72	41.86	-0.14	428	"	81	.71	428	"	81	88.7	45.69	46.31	-0.62	421	"	88	.81	419	"	90	98	50.48	50.10	+0.38	nc 421	"	88	.91	nc 412	"	97	103.3	53.21	53.21	0.00	c 410	"	99	1.01	c 405	"	104	106.3	54.75	55.38	-0.63	nc 404	"	105	1.11	c 408	"	101	111	57.17	57.40	-0.23	c 404	"	105	1.21	c 403	"	106	113.5	58.46	58.40	+0.06	c 402	510	108	1.31	c 400	512	112	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30	nc 402	"	110	1.41	c 393	"	119	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	c 396	511	115 ×	1.31	c 400	512	112 ×	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30	394	"	118	1.41	e 401	509	108	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	nc 397	"	115	1.41	e 396	508	112	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	e 397	"	111						
.085	495.5	"	14.5	14.5	7.47	7.34	+0.13																																																																																																																																																																																																																							
	495.5	"	14.5					.11	489	"	21	21	10.82	9.41	+1.41	489	"	21	.16	483	509	26 ×	26	13.39	13.41	-0.02	482	507	25	.21	482	"	25	36	18.54	17.25	+1.29	470	506	36	.31	470	"	36	47.5	24.46	24.41	+0.05	459	"	47	.41	458	"	48	60	30.90	30.90	0.00	448	"	58	.51	446	508	62	69	35.54	36.71	-1.17	439	"	69	.61	440	509	69	81	41.72	41.86	-0.14	428	"	81	.71	428	"	81	88.7	45.69	46.31	-0.62	421	"	88	.81	419	"	90	98	50.48	50.10	+0.38	nc 421	"	88	.91	nc 412	"	97	103.3	53.21	53.21	0.00	c 410	"	99	1.01	c 405	"	104	106.3	54.75	55.38	-0.63	nc 404	"	105	1.11	c 408	"	101	111	57.17	57.40	-0.23	c 404	"	105	1.21	c 403	"	106	113.5	58.46	58.40	+0.06	c 402	510	108	1.31	c 400	512	112	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30	nc 402	"	110	1.41	c 393	"	119	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	c 396	511	115 ×	1.31	c 400	512	112 ×	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30	394	"	118	1.41	e 401	509	108	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	nc 397	"	115	1.41	e 396	508	112	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	e 397	"	111																	
.11	489	"	21	21	10.82	9.41	+1.41																																																																																																																																																																																																																							
	489	"	21					.16	483	509	26 ×	26	13.39	13.41	-0.02	482	507	25	.21	482	"	25	36	18.54	17.25	+1.29	470	506	36	.31	470	"	36	47.5	24.46	24.41	+0.05	459	"	47	.41	458	"	48	60	30.90	30.90	0.00	448	"	58	.51	446	508	62	69	35.54	36.71	-1.17	439	"	69	.61	440	509	69	81	41.72	41.86	-0.14	428	"	81	.71	428	"	81	88.7	45.69	46.31	-0.62	421	"	88	.81	419	"	90	98	50.48	50.10	+0.38	nc 421	"	88	.91	nc 412	"	97	103.3	53.21	53.21	0.00	c 410	"	99	1.01	c 405	"	104	106.3	54.75	55.38	-0.63	nc 404	"	105	1.11	c 408	"	101	111	57.17	57.40	-0.23	c 404	"	105	1.21	c 403	"	106	113.5	58.46	58.40	+0.06	c 402	510	108	1.31	c 400	512	112	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30	nc 402	"	110	1.41	c 393	"	119	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	c 396	511	115 ×	1.31	c 400	512	112 ×	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30	394	"	118	1.41	e 401	509	108	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	nc 397	"	115	1.41	e 396	508	112	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	e 397	"	111																												
.16	483	509	26 ×	26	13.39	13.41	-0.02																																																																																																																																																																																																																							
	482	507	25					.21	482	"	25	36	18.54	17.25	+1.29	470	506	36	.31	470	"	36	47.5	24.46	24.41	+0.05	459	"	47	.41	458	"	48	60	30.90	30.90	0.00	448	"	58	.51	446	508	62	69	35.54	36.71	-1.17	439	"	69	.61	440	509	69	81	41.72	41.86	-0.14	428	"	81	.71	428	"	81	88.7	45.69	46.31	-0.62	421	"	88	.81	419	"	90	98	50.48	50.10	+0.38	nc 421	"	88	.91	nc 412	"	97	103.3	53.21	53.21	0.00	c 410	"	99	1.01	c 405	"	104	106.3	54.75	55.38	-0.63	nc 404	"	105	1.11	c 408	"	101	111	57.17	57.40	-0.23	c 404	"	105	1.21	c 403	"	106	113.5	58.46	58.40	+0.06	c 402	510	108	1.31	c 400	512	112	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30	nc 402	"	110	1.41	c 393	"	119	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	c 396	511	115 ×	1.31	c 400	512	112 ×	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30	394	"	118	1.41	e 401	509	108	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	nc 397	"	115	1.41	e 396	508	112	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	e 397	"	111																																							
.21	482	"	25	36	18.54	17.25	+1.29																																																																																																																																																																																																																							
	470	506	36					.31	470	"	36	47.5	24.46	24.41	+0.05	459	"	47	.41	458	"	48	60	30.90	30.90	0.00	448	"	58	.51	446	508	62	69	35.54	36.71	-1.17	439	"	69	.61	440	509	69	81	41.72	41.86	-0.14	428	"	81	.71	428	"	81	88.7	45.69	46.31	-0.62	421	"	88	.81	419	"	90	98	50.48	50.10	+0.38	nc 421	"	88	.91	nc 412	"	97	103.3	53.21	53.21	0.00	c 410	"	99	1.01	c 405	"	104	106.3	54.75	55.38	-0.63	nc 404	"	105	1.11	c 408	"	101	111	57.17	57.40	-0.23	c 404	"	105	1.21	c 403	"	106	113.5	58.46	58.40	+0.06	c 402	510	108	1.31	c 400	512	112	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30	nc 402	"	110	1.41	c 393	"	119	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	c 396	511	115 ×	1.31	c 400	512	112 ×	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30	394	"	118	1.41	e 401	509	108	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	nc 397	"	115	1.41	e 396	508	112	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	e 397	"	111																																																		
.31	470	"	36	47.5	24.46	24.41	+0.05																																																																																																																																																																																																																							
	459	"	47					.41	458	"	48	60	30.90	30.90	0.00	448	"	58	.51	446	508	62	69	35.54	36.71	-1.17	439	"	69	.61	440	509	69	81	41.72	41.86	-0.14	428	"	81	.71	428	"	81	88.7	45.69	46.31	-0.62	421	"	88	.81	419	"	90	98	50.48	50.10	+0.38	nc 421	"	88	.91	nc 412	"	97	103.3	53.21	53.21	0.00	c 410	"	99	1.01	c 405	"	104	106.3	54.75	55.38	-0.63	nc 404	"	105	1.11	c 408	"	101	111	57.17	57.40	-0.23	c 404	"	105	1.21	c 403	"	106	113.5	58.46	58.40	+0.06	c 402	510	108	1.31	c 400	512	112	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30	nc 402	"	110	1.41	c 393	"	119	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	c 396	511	115 ×	1.31	c 400	512	112 ×	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30	394	"	118	1.41	e 401	509	108	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	nc 397	"	115	1.41	e 396	508	112	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	e 397	"	111																																																													
.41	458	"	48	60	30.90	30.90	0.00																																																																																																																																																																																																																							
	448	"	58					.51	446	508	62	69	35.54	36.71	-1.17	439	"	69	.61	440	509	69	81	41.72	41.86	-0.14	428	"	81	.71	428	"	81	88.7	45.69	46.31	-0.62	421	"	88	.81	419	"	90	98	50.48	50.10	+0.38	nc 421	"	88	.91	nc 412	"	97	103.3	53.21	53.21	0.00	c 410	"	99	1.01	c 405	"	104	106.3	54.75	55.38	-0.63	nc 404	"	105	1.11	c 408	"	101	111	57.17	57.40	-0.23	c 404	"	105	1.21	c 403	"	106	113.5	58.46	58.40	+0.06	c 402	510	108	1.31	c 400	512	112	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30	nc 402	"	110	1.41	c 393	"	119	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	c 396	511	115 ×	1.31	c 400	512	112 ×	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30	394	"	118	1.41	e 401	509	108	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	nc 397	"	115	1.41	e 396	508	112	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	e 397	"	111																																																																								
.51	446	508	62	69	35.54	36.71	-1.17																																																																																																																																																																																																																							
	439	"	69					.61	440	509	69	81	41.72	41.86	-0.14	428	"	81	.71	428	"	81	88.7	45.69	46.31	-0.62	421	"	88	.81	419	"	90	98	50.48	50.10	+0.38	nc 421	"	88	.91	nc 412	"	97	103.3	53.21	53.21	0.00	c 410	"	99	1.01	c 405	"	104	106.3	54.75	55.38	-0.63	nc 404	"	105	1.11	c 408	"	101	111	57.17	57.40	-0.23	c 404	"	105	1.21	c 403	"	106	113.5	58.46	58.40	+0.06	c 402	510	108	1.31	c 400	512	112	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30	nc 402	"	110	1.41	c 393	"	119	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	c 396	511	115 ×	1.31	c 400	512	112 ×	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30	394	"	118	1.41	e 401	509	108	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	nc 397	"	115	1.41	e 396	508	112	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	e 397	"	111																																																																																			
.61	440	509	69	81	41.72	41.86	-0.14																																																																																																																																																																																																																							
	428	"	81					.71	428	"	81	88.7	45.69	46.31	-0.62	421	"	88	.81	419	"	90	98	50.48	50.10	+0.38	nc 421	"	88	.91	nc 412	"	97	103.3	53.21	53.21	0.00	c 410	"	99	1.01	c 405	"	104	106.3	54.75	55.38	-0.63	nc 404	"	105	1.11	c 408	"	101	111	57.17	57.40	-0.23	c 404	"	105	1.21	c 403	"	106	113.5	58.46	58.40	+0.06	c 402	510	108	1.31	c 400	512	112	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30	nc 402	"	110	1.41	c 393	"	119	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	c 396	511	115 ×	1.31	c 400	512	112 ×	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30	394	"	118	1.41	e 401	509	108	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	nc 397	"	115	1.41	e 396	508	112	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	e 397	"	111																																																																																														
.71	428	"	81	88.7	45.69	46.31	-0.62																																																																																																																																																																																																																							
	421	"	88					.81	419	"	90	98	50.48	50.10	+0.38	nc 421	"	88	.91	nc 412	"	97	103.3	53.21	53.21	0.00	c 410	"	99	1.01	c 405	"	104	106.3	54.75	55.38	-0.63	nc 404	"	105	1.11	c 408	"	101	111	57.17	57.40	-0.23	c 404	"	105	1.21	c 403	"	106	113.5	58.46	58.40	+0.06	c 402	510	108	1.31	c 400	512	112	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30	nc 402	"	110	1.41	c 393	"	119	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	c 396	511	115 ×	1.31	c 400	512	112 ×	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30	394	"	118	1.41	e 401	509	108	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	nc 397	"	115	1.41	e 396	508	112	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	e 397	"	111																																																																																																									
.81	419	"	90	98	50.48	50.10	+0.38																																																																																																																																																																																																																							
	nc 421	"	88					.91	nc 412	"	97	103.3	53.21	53.21	0.00	c 410	"	99	1.01	c 405	"	104	106.3	54.75	55.38	-0.63	nc 404	"	105	1.11	c 408	"	101	111	57.17	57.40	-0.23	c 404	"	105	1.21	c 403	"	106	113.5	58.46	58.40	+0.06	c 402	510	108	1.31	c 400	512	112	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30	nc 402	"	110	1.41	c 393	"	119	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	c 396	511	115 ×	1.31	c 400	512	112 ×	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30	394	"	118	1.41	e 401	509	108	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	nc 397	"	115	1.41	e 396	508	112	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	e 397	"	111																																																																																																																				
.91	nc 412	"	97	103.3	53.21	53.21	0.00																																																																																																																																																																																																																							
	c 410	"	99					1.01	c 405	"	104	106.3	54.75	55.38	-0.63	nc 404	"	105	1.11	c 408	"	101	111	57.17	57.40	-0.23	c 404	"	105	1.21	c 403	"	106	113.5	58.46	58.40	+0.06	c 402	510	108	1.31	c 400	512	112	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30	nc 402	"	110	1.41	c 393	"	119	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	c 396	511	115 ×	1.31	c 400	512	112 ×	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30	394	"	118	1.41	e 401	509	108	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	nc 397	"	115	1.41	e 396	508	112	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	e 397	"	111																																																																																																																															
1.01	c 405	"	104	106.3	54.75	55.38	-0.63																																																																																																																																																																																																																							
	nc 404	"	105					1.11	c 408	"	101	111	57.17	57.40	-0.23	c 404	"	105	1.21	c 403	"	106	113.5	58.46	58.40	+0.06	c 402	510	108	1.31	c 400	512	112	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30	nc 402	"	110	1.41	c 393	"	119	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	c 396	511	115 ×	1.31	c 400	512	112 ×	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30	394	"	118	1.41	e 401	509	108	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	nc 397	"	115	1.41	e 396	508	112	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	e 397	"	111																																																																																																																																										
1.11	c 408	"	101	111	57.17	57.40	-0.23																																																																																																																																																																																																																							
	c 404	"	105					1.21	c 403	"	106	113.5	58.46	58.40	+0.06	c 402	510	108	1.31	c 400	512	112	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30	nc 402	"	110	1.41	c 393	"	119	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	c 396	511	115 ×	1.31	c 400	512	112 ×	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30	394	"	118	1.41	e 401	509	108	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	nc 397	"	115	1.41	e 396	508	112	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	e 397	"	111																																																																																																																																																					
1.21	c 403	"	106	113.5	58.46	58.40	+0.06																																																																																																																																																																																																																							
	c 402	510	108					1.31	c 400	512	112	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30	nc 402	"	110	1.41	c 393	"	119	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	c 396	511	115 ×	1.31	c 400	512	112 ×	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30	394	"	118	1.41	e 401	509	108	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	nc 397	"	115	1.41	e 396	508	112	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	e 397	"	111																																																																																																																																																																
1.31	c 400	512	112	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30																																																																																																																																																																																																																							
	nc 402	"	110					1.41	c 393	"	119	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	c 396	511	115 ×	1.31	c 400	512	112 ×	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30	394	"	118	1.41	e 401	509	108	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	nc 397	"	115	1.41	e 396	508	112	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	e 397	"	111																																																																																																																																																																											
1.41	c 393	"	119	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92																																																																																																																																																																																																																							
	c 396	511	115 ×					1.31	c 400	512	112 ×	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30	394	"	118	1.41	e 401	509	108	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	nc 397	"	115	1.41	e 396	508	112	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	e 397	"	111																																																																																																																																																																																						
1.31	c 400	512	112 ×	113.7	58.56	58.86	-0.30																																																																																																																																																																																																																							
	394	"	118					1.41	e 401	509	108	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	nc 397	"	115	1.41	e 396	508	112	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	e 397	"	111																																																																																																																																																																																																	
1.41	e 401	509	108	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92																																																																																																																																																																																																																							
	nc 397	"	115					1.41	e 396	508	112	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92	e 397	"	111																																																																																																																																																																																																												
1.41	e 396	508	112	111.7	57.69	58.61	-0.92																																																																																																																																																																																																																							
	e 397	"	111																																																																																																																																																																																																																											

TABLE XIV.—Distance Curve, discs having first been heated, 20th July 1877.
Dielectric, Air. Electrodes, large discs. Pressure, 740 mm.

Equation, $V = 87\cdot040s - 19\cdot560s^2$.

Length of Spark in Centimetres. <i>s</i> .	Deflection. <i>n</i> .	Zero. <i>n</i> ¹ .	Observed Diff. of Potential. <i>n</i> ¹ - <i>n</i> .	Mean Diff. of Potential.	Mean Diff. of Potential in absolute measure. <i>V</i> ¹ .	Calculated Diff. of Potential in abs. meas. <i>V</i> .	Difference <i>V</i> ¹ - <i>V</i> .
.05	510	523	13	11.5	4.50	4.30	+0.20
	513		10				
.1	500	"	23	23	8.99	8.51	+0.48
.15	488	"	35	35	13.69	12.62	+1.07
.2	477	"	46	46	17.99	16.63	+1.36
.25	473	"	50	50	19.56	20.54	-0.98
.35	450	"	73	73	28.56	28.07	+0.49
.45	433	"	90	90	35.21	35.21	0.00
.55	420	"	103	103	40.29	41.95	-1.66
.65	401	"	122	122	47.72	48.31	-0.59
.75	383	"	140	140	54.76	54.28	+0.48
.85	370	"	153	153	59.85	59.85	0.00
.95	358	"	165	165	64.54	65.03	-0.49
1.05	e 343	"	180	179	70.02	69.83	+0.19
	e 345		178				
.25	474	"	49	...	...	...	...
	473		50				

Taken after an interval of 45 minutes :—

.25	468	523	55	...	...	...	...
	471.1		51.5				
.5	423	520	97	...	...	...	...
	423		97				

TABLE XV.—Change of Capacity of Charged Conductor, 4th July 1877.
Dielectric, Air. Electrodes, large discs. Pressure, atmospheric. Length of spark, .5 centimetres.

Capacity.	Deflection. <i>n</i> .	Zero. <i>n</i> ¹ .	Diff. of Potential. <i>n</i> ¹ - <i>n</i> .	Mean Diff. of Potential.	
Large jar,	}	300	500	200	} 203
		295	496	201	
		290	490	200	
		293	486	193	
		296	505	209	
		297	"	208	
		296	"	209	

TABLE XV.—*continued.*

Capacity.	Deflection. <i>n.</i>	Zero. <i>n</i> ¹ .	Diff. of Potential. <i>n</i> ¹ - <i>n.</i>	Mean Diff. of Potential.
Couple of small jars, }	298	505	207	} 207
	300	"	205	
	296	"	209	
	300	"	205	
	296	"	209	
Without any jars, . }	315	510	295	} 209
	295	"	215	
	310	"	200	
	290	"	220	
	290	"	220	
	305	"	205	
	300	"	210	

TABLE XVI.—Distance Curve ; Continued Discharge, 17th July 1877.
Dielectric, Air. Electrodes, large discs. Pressure, 737 mm.

$$\text{Equation, } V = \{46.095 - 2.567s\} \sqrt{\{s^2 + .2s\}}.$$

Length of Spark in Centimetres. <i>s.</i>	Deflection <i>n.</i>	Zero. <i>n</i> ¹ .	Observed Diff. of Potential. <i>n</i> ¹ - <i>n.</i>	Diff. of Potential in absolute measure. <i>V</i> ¹ .	Calculated Diff. of Potential. <i>V.</i>	Difference <i>V</i> ¹ - <i>V.</i>
.06	494	510	16	4.55	5.74	-1.19
.11	487	518	31	8.81	8.46	+0.35
.21	483	530	47	13.35	13.34	+0.01
.31	473	540	67	19.03	18.01	+1.02
.41	475	560	85	24.14	22.53	+1.61
.51	463	545	82	23.29	26.95	-2.66
.61	452	554	102	38.97	31.30	-2.33
.71	450	570	120	34.08	35.59	-1.51
.81	438	565	127	36.07	39.81	-3.74
.91	<i>e</i>	...	...	...	...	...
.51 {	438	520	82	} ...	...	...
	447	530	83		...	...

TABLE XVII.—Pressure Curve, 3d July. First Curve. Jars on. Dielectric, Air. Electrodes, large discs. Length of spark, .5 centimetre.

$$\text{Equation, } V = \{.048646 - .0000033047p\} \sqrt{\{p^2 + 200p\}}.$$

Pressure in Millimetres of Mercury. <i>p</i> .	Deflection. <i>n</i> .	Zero. <i>n</i> ¹ .	Observed Diff. of Potential. <i>n</i> ¹ - <i>n</i> .	Mean Diff. of Potential.	Mean Diff. of Potential in absolute measure. <i>V</i> ¹ .	Calculated Diff. of Potential in abs. meas. <i>V</i> .	Difference. <i>V</i> ¹ - <i>V</i> .
20	486	510	24	24	3.23	3.22	+0.01
	486	"	24				
40	476	509	33	32.5	4.37	4.76	-0.39
	477	"	32				
60	464	511	47	47	6.33	6.06	+0.27
	464	"	47				
80	460	"	51	52	7.00	7.26	-0.26
	459	"	52 x				
100	448	"	63	63	8.48	8.39	+0.09
	448	"	63				
120	440	513	73	72.5	9.76	9.49	+0.27
	440	512	72				
140	433	"	79	80.5	10.84	10.56	+0.28
	430	"	82				
160	425	"	87	87	11.71	11.61	+0.10
	425	"	87				
180	414	"	98	98	13.19	12.64	+0.55
	414	"	98				
200	408	"	104	104	14.00	13.66	+0.34
	408	"	104				
303	368	510	142	139	18.71	18.81	-0.10
	364	505	141				
406	373	"	132	17.5	23.56	23.84	-0.28
	366	506	140				
509	338	508	170 x	206	27.73	28.81	-1.08
	325	"	183				
612	332	"	176 x	242	32.57	33.73	-1.16
	330	"	178 x				
685	304	"	204	268	36.07	37.18	-1.11
	305	"	203				
685	298	"	210	268	36.07	37.18	-1.11
	302	"	206				
685	270	"	238	268	36.07	37.18	-1.11
	265	"	243				
685	265	"	243	268	36.07	37.18	-1.11
	266	"	242				
685	242	"	266	268	36.07	37.18	-1.11
	235	"	273				
685	240	"	268	268	36.07	37.18	-1.11
	240	"	268				

TABLE XVIII.—Pressure Curve, 3d July. Second Curve. Without jars on. Dielectric, Air. Electrodes, large discs. Length of spark, .5 centimetre.

Equation, $V = .04455 \sqrt{\{p^2 + 200p\}}$.

Pressure in mm. of Mercury. <i>p</i> .	Deflection. <i>n</i> .	Zero. <i>n</i> ² .	Observed Diff. of Potential. <i>n</i> ² - <i>n</i> .	Mean Diff. of Potential.	Mean Diff. of Potential in absolute measure. $\sqrt{V}$.	Calculated Diff. of Potential. <i>V</i> .	Difference. <i>V</i> ² - <i>V</i> .
25	492	512	20	} 20.3	2.73	3.34	-0.61
	492	"	20				
	491	"	21				
40	482	"	30 ×	} 30	4.04	4.36	-0.32
	484	"	28				
60	472	"	40	} 41	5.52	5.56	-0.04
	470	"	42				
80	460	"	52	} 52	7.00	6.67	+0.33
	460	"	52				
100	454	"	58	} 58.5	7.87	7.72	+0.15
	453	"	59				
120	443	"	69	} 69	9.29	8.73	+0.56
	443	"	69				
140	440	513	73	} 73	9.83	9.72	+0.11
	440	"	73				
160	435	"	78	} 79	10.63	10.69	-0.06
	433	"	80				
180	429	"	84	} 86	11.58	11.65	-0.07
	425	"	88				
200	418	"	95	} 95	12.79	12.60	+0.19
	418	"	95				
303	385	"	128 ×	} 128	17.23	17.39	-0.16
	388	"	125				
406	355	"	158	} 165	22.21	22.10	+0.11
	340	"	173				
	346	"	167				
	348	"	165				
509	313	"	200 ×	} 200	26.92	26.73	+0.19
	308	"	205				
612	280	"	233	} 233	31.36	31.41	-0.05
	280	"	233				

TABLE XIX.—Pressure Curve, 27th June 1877. Dielectric, Air. Electrodes large discs. Length of spark, .5 centimetre.

$$\text{Equation, } V = \cdot 046342 \sqrt{\{p^2 + 199\cdot 01p\}}.$$

Pressure in mm. of Mercury. <i>p.</i>	Deflection. <i>n.</i>	Zero. <i>n</i> ¹ .	Observed Diff. of Potential. <i>n</i> ¹ - <i>n.</i>	Mean Diff. of Potential.	Mean Diff. of Potential in absolute measure. <i>V</i> ¹ .	Calculated Diff. of Potential in abs. meas. <i>V.</i>	Difference. <i>V</i> ¹ - <i>V.</i>
66	479	514	35	35	6.13	6.13	0.00
	479	"	35				
	479	"	35				
169	447	513	66	66	11.56	11.56	0.00
	447	"	66				
	447	"	66				
273	415	508	93	90	15.75	13.91	+1.84
	418	"	90 ×				
	414	510	96				
376	392	508	116	119	20.83	21.55	-0.72
	389	"	119 ×				
	393	510	117				
479	358	"	152 ×	152	26.60	26.41	+0.19
	360	515	155				
	356	"	159				
582	351	518	167	177	30.98	31.24	-0.26
	343	520	177 ×				
	350	523	173				
740	295	510	215 ×	215	37.63	38.63	-1.00
	310	517	207				
	318	525	207				

TABLE XX.—Pressure Curves, 29th June 1877. First Curve. Single Discharge. Dielectric, Air. Electrodes, large discs. Length of spark, .5 centimetre.

$$\text{Equation, } V = \cdot 046853 \sqrt{\{p^2 + 207\cdot 06p\}}.$$

Pressure in mm. of Mercury. <i>p.</i>	Deflection. <i>n.</i>	Zero. <i>n</i> ¹ .	Difference of Potential. <i>n</i> ¹ - <i>n.</i>	Mean Diff. of Potential.	Mean Diff. of Potential in absolute measure. <i>V</i> ¹ .	Calculated Diff. of Potential in abs. meas. <i>V.</i>	Difference. <i>V</i> ¹ - <i>V.</i>
20	478	495	17	20	3.13	3.16	-0.03
	475	"	20 ×				
	477	"	18				
60	490	530	40	39	6.11	5.93	+0.18
	490	529	39 ×				
	490	"	39 ×				

TABLE XX.—*continued.*

Pressure in mm. of Mercury. <i>p.</i>	Deflection. <i>n.</i>	Zero. <i>n</i> ¹ .	Difference of Potential. <i>n</i> ¹ — <i>n.</i>	Mean Diff. of Potential.	Mean Diff. of Potential in absolute measure. <i>v</i> ¹ .	Calculated Diff. of Potential in abs. meas. <i>V.</i>	Difference. <i>V</i> ¹ — <i>V.</i>
100	465	515	50	52	8.15	8.20	-0.05
	452	510	58				
	461	"	49				
140	468	533	65	65	10.19	10.30	-0.11
	467	532	65				
	464	530	66				
180	430	510	80	80	12.54	12.29	+0.25
	430	"	80				
	428	508	80				
200	418	507	89	86.5	13.56	13.30	+0.26
	424	505	81				
	416	"	89				
40	483	510	27 ×	29.5	4.62	4.66	-0.04
	484	"	26				
	478	"	32 ×				
80	470	512	42	44	6.90	7.10	-0.20
	467	"	45				
	467	"	45				
120	458	517	59	60	9.40	9.27	+0.13
	455	516	61				
	455	"	61				
160	443	517	74	72	11.28	11.32	-0.04
	443	516	73				
	448	517	69				
10	502	511	9	11	1.72	2.18	-0.46
	500	510	10				
	498	509	11 ×				

Second Curve. Continued Discharge.

Equation, $V = (.03552 - .000002413p) \sqrt{\{p^2 + 200p\}}$.

20	479	495	16	2.56	2.35	+0.21
60	502	529	27	4.32	4.42	-0.10
100	473	510	37	5.92	6.11	-0.19
140	479	530	51	8.16	7.68	+0.48
180	450	508	58	9.28	9.18	+0.10
200	443	506	63	10.08	9.91	+0.17
40	488	511	23	3.68	3.47	+0.21
80	483	515	32	5.12	5.29	-0.17
120	478	518	40	6.40	6.90	-0.50
160	470	520	50	8.00	8.43	-0.43
10	502	516	14	2.24	1.63	+0.61

TABLE XXI.—Pressure Curve, 15th June 1877. Longer Spark. Dielectric, Air. Electrodes, large discs. Length of spark, 1 centimetre.

$$\text{Equation, } V = \cdot 080620 \sqrt{\{p^2 + 219\cdot 84p\}}.$$

Pressure in mm. of Mercury. <i>p</i> .	Deflection. <i>n</i> .	Zero. <i>n</i> ¹ .	Observed Diff. of Potential. <i>n</i> ¹ - <i>n</i> .	Mean Diff. of Potential.	Mean Diff. of Potential in absolute measure. <i>V</i> ¹ .	Calculated Diff. of Potential. <i>V</i> .	Difference. <i>V</i> ¹ - <i>V</i> .
20	485	505	20	} 20·4	5·59	5·58	+0·01
	486	"	19				
	484	506	22				
40	478	507	29	} 29·3	8·03	8·22	-0·19
	478	"	29				
	477	"	30				
60	470	"	37	} 38	10·41	10·45	-0·04
	468	506	38				
	468	"	38				
80	459	"	47	} 46	12·60	12·49	+0·11
	461	"	45				
	460	"	46				
100	455	508	53	} 53	14·52	14·42	+0·10
	453	507	54				
	455	"	52				
120	444	508	64	} 63	17·26	16·28	+0·98
	444	507	63				
	444	"	63				
140	435	"	72	} 71	19·45	18·10	+1·35
	435	"	72				
	436	"	71 ×				
160	423	"	84	} 83	22·74	19·87	+2·87
	424	"	83 ×				
	423	"	84				
180	418	508	90	} 84	23·01	21·63	+1·38
	422	509	87				
	425	"	84 ×				
200	408	500	92	} 89	24·38	23·36	+1·02
	408	502	94				
	415	504	89 ×				
740	268	513	245	} 248	67·94	67·94	0·00
	266	517	251				

TABLE XXII.—Pressure Curve, 12th July 1877. Dielectric, Hydrogen. Electrodes, large discs. Length of spark, 5 centimetre. Temperature, 70° Fahr.

Equation, $V = .024 \sqrt{\{p^2 + 600p\}}$.

Pressure in mm. of Mercury. <i>p</i> .	Deflection. <i>n</i> .	Zero. <i>n</i> ¹ .	Observed Diff. of Potential. <i>n</i> ¹ - <i>n</i> .	Mean Diff. of Potential.	Mean Diff. of Potential in absolute measure. <i>V</i> ¹ .	Calculated Diff. of Potential. <i>V</i> .	Difference. <i>V</i> ¹ - <i>V</i> .
752	439	511	72	72.5	24.03	24.20	-0.07
	438		73				
648	445	510	65 ×	65	21.62	21.09	+0.53
	455		55				
572	450	"	60	59.5	19.81	19.65	+0.16
	452		58				
468	450	512	60	51	16.98	16.97	+0.01
	461		51				
364	470	"	42	42	13.98	14.22	-0.24
	471		41				
262	470	"	42	31	10.32	11.41	-1.09
	481		31				
158	481	"	31	25	8.32	8.31	+0.01
	485		27				
56	488	"	24	15	4.99	4.60	+0.39
	487		25				
31	495	"	17	10	3.33	3.36	-0.03
	497		15 ×				
	500	"	12				
	502		10 ×				

TABLE XXIII.—The Electric Strength of Different Gases, 5th July 1877. Electrodes, large discs. Pressure, 746 mm. Length of spark, 5 centimetre.

Dielectric.	Deflection. <i>n</i> .	Zero. <i>n</i> ¹ .	Diff. of Potential. <i>n</i> ¹ - <i>n</i> .	Mean Diff. of Potential.	Electric Strength relative to that of Air.	Mean of all other Observations	Faraday's Values.
Air . . .	350	501	151	152	...	...	...
	360		141				
	348	"	153				
	344	"	157				
	347	502	155				
	352	"	150				
	350	"	152				
	345	"	157				

TABLE XXIII—*continued.*

Dielectric.	Deflection. <i>n</i> .	Zero. <i>n</i> ¹ .	Diff. of Potential. <i>n</i> ¹ - <i>n</i> .	Mean Diff. of Potential.	Electric Strength relative to that of Air.	Mean of all other Observations.	Faraday's Values.
CO ₂ , . .	370	502	132	} 135	·951	·952	·91
	363	"	139				
	364	505	141				
	373	503	130				
	369	"	134				
	363	505	142				
	374	"	131				
	368	"	137				
	364	507	143				
	380	"	127				
377	"	130					
Air, . .	368	"	139	} 142	1·000	...	...
	365	"	142				
	370	"	137				
	360	"	147				
	360	"	147				
	367	"	140				
O ₂ , . .	370	505	135	} 132	·930	·938	·71
	372	"	133				
	372	"	133				
	370	"	135				
	380	"	125				
	373	"	132				
	373	"	132				
Air, . .	356	503	147	} 142	...	...	...
	370	"	133				
	366	"	137				
	358	"	145				
	356	"	147				
H ₂ , .	417	505	88	} 90	·634	·664	·53
	420	510	90				
	420	"	90				
	420	"	90				
	420	511	91				
	420	512	92				
	423	"	89				
Air, . .	375	510	135	} 141	...	...	...
	368	"	142				
	368	"	142				
	365	"	145				
Coal Gas,	...	...	...	...	...	·935	·71

TABLE XXIV.—Long Distance Curve, 25th May 1877. Dielectric, Air.
Electrodes, balls. Pressure, 85 mm. Temperature, 66° Fahr.

$$\text{Equation, } V = 34 \cdot 92s^{\frac{1}{2}} - 1 \cdot 206s^{\frac{3}{2}}.$$

Length of Spark in Centimetres. s.	Deflection. n.	Zero. n.	Observed Diff. of Potential. $n^1 - n.$	Mean Diff. of Potential. $V^1.$	Calculated Diff. of Potential. V.	Difference. $V^1 - V.$	
14	}	500	88	}	89.3	67.5	+21.8
			90				
			90				
13	}	"	87	}	88.3	69.4	+18.9
			90				
			88				
12	}	"	87	}	87	70.8	+16.2
			87				
			87				
11	}	"	80	}	84	71.8	+12.2
			85				
			86				
10	}	"	81	}	80.3	72.3	+8.0
			80				
			80				
9	}	"	80	}	80.3	72.2	+8.1
			81				
			80				
8	}	"	72	}	72	71.5	+0.5
			72				
			72				
7	}	"	66	}	70	70.0	0.0
			70 x				
			70 x				
6	}	"	69	}	67.7	67.8	-0.1
			67				
			67				
5	}	"	66	}	64.7	64.6	+0.1
			65				
			63				
4	}	"	61	}	60	60.2	-0.2
			59				
			60				
3	}	"	56	}	54.3	54.2	+0.1
			53				
			54				
2	}	"	50	}	48.3	46.0	+2.3
			47				
			48				
1	}	"	34	}	34.7	33.7	+1.0
			37				
			33				
.5	}	"	28	}	24.3	24.3	0.0
			20				
			25				

TABLE XXV.—Long Distance Curve, 22d May 1877. Dielectric, Air.
Electrodes, balls. Pressure, 40 mm.

$$\text{Equation, } V = 16.752s^{\frac{1}{2}} - .6364s^{\frac{3}{2}}.$$

Length of Spark in Centimetres. <i>s</i> .	Deflection. <i>n</i> .	Zero. <i>n</i> ¹ .	Observed Diff. of Potential. <i>n</i> ¹ - <i>n</i> .	Mean Diff. of Potential. <i>V</i> ¹ .	Calculated Diff. of Potential. <i>V</i> .	Difference. <i>V</i> ¹ - <i>V</i> .
1	480	496	16	16.3	16.1	+0.2
	479	"	17			
	480	"	16			
2	473	"	23	23	21.9	+1.1
	473	"	23			
	473	"	23			
3	470	"	26	25.7	25.7	0.0
	472	"	24			
	469	"	27			
4	470	"	26	27.3	28.4	-1.1
	468	"	28			
	468	"	28			
5	467	"	29	29.3	30.3	-1.0
	467	"	29			
	466	"	30			
6	465	"	31	30.7	31.7	-1.0
	466	"	30			
	465	"	31			
7	463	"	33	32.7	32.5	+0.2
	465	"	31			
	462	"	34			
8	463	"	33	32.7	33.0	-0.3
	463	"	33			
	464	"	32			
9	460	"	36	35.3	33.1	+2.2
	461	"	35			
	461	"	35			

TABLE XXVI.—Long Distance Curve, 23d May 1877. Dielectric, Air.
Electrodes, balls. Pressure, 20 mm.

Equation, $V = 7.4405s^{\frac{1}{2}} - .16580s^{\frac{3}{2}}$.

Length of Spark. s.	Deflection. n.	Zero. n ¹ .	Observed Diff. of Potential. n ¹ - n.	Mean Diff. of Potential. V ¹ .	Calculated Diff. of Potential. V.	Difference. V ¹ - V.	Temperature.
1	491	500	9 ×	9	7.3	+1.7	...
	488		12				
	491		9 ×				
2	488	500	12	10	10.1	-0.1	64.5° F.
	489		11				
	490		10 ×				
3	489	500	11	11.3	12.0	-0.7	...
	488		12				
	489		11				
4	488	500	12	12	13.6	-1.6	...
	488		12				
	487		13				
5	487	500	13	14	14.8	-0.8	...
	486		14 ×				
	486		14				
6	488	503	15 ×	15	15.8	-0.8	66°
	488		15				
	486		17				
7	487	503	16	16.7	16.6	+0.1	...
	486		17				
	486		17				
8	486	503	17	17	17.3	-0.3	...
	486		17				
	486		17				
9	485	503	18	17.5	17.8	-0.3	66.4°
	486		17				
	485.5		17.5				
10	483	502	19	18.7	18.3	+0.4	...
	483		19				
	484		18				
11	483	503	19	18.3	18.6	-0.3	...
	485		18				
	484		19				
12	483	503	20	19.3	18.9	+0.4	66.5°
	484		19				
	481		19				
13	483	503	20	19.3	19.1	+0.2	...
	485		19				
	482		21				
14	483	504	20	21	19.2	+1.8	67°
	482		22				
	482		21				
15	480	503	23	22	19.2	+2.8	...
	482		22				

TABLE XXVII.—Long Distance Curve, 17th May 1877. Dielectric, Air.
Electrodes, small balls. Pressure, 30 mm.

$$\text{Equation, } V = 13.168s^{\frac{1}{2}} - .40519s^{\frac{3}{2}}.$$

Length of Spark. s.	Deflection. n.	Zero. n^1 .	Observed Diff. of Potential. $n^2 - n$.	Mean Diff. of Potential. V^1 .	Calculated Diff. of Potential. V.	Difference. $V^1 - V$.
1	470	487	17	16	12.8	+3.4
	471	"	16 ×			
	471	"	16 ×			
2	468	"	19	18	17.5	+0.5
	469	"	18			
	470	"	17			
2.5	467	"	20	19.3	19.2	+0.1
	467	"	20			
	469	"	18			
5	465	"	22	22.5	24.9	-2.4
	465	"	22			
	464.5	"	22.5 ×			
7.5	464	"	23	25.5	27.7	-2.2
	462	"	25 ×			
	461	"	26 ×			
10	458	"	29	28.7	28.8	-0.1
	458	"	29			
	459	"	28			
12.5	458	"	29	28.3	28.6	-0.3
	459	"	28			
	459	"	28			
15	457	"	30	29	27.5	+1.5
	460	"	27			
	457	"	30			
17.5	454	"	33	33.3	25.4	+7.9
	454	"	33			
	453	"	34			

TABLE XXVIII.—Comparison of Electrometers, 10th July 1877.

Mean of eight determinations, 38·63 C. G. S. units.

Distance between Plates of Absolute Electrometer in mm. D.	Deflection of Electrometer at moment of fall of Aluminium Square.	Zero.	Difference, giving Reading of Divided Ring Electrometer.	Mean Difference.	Value in absolute measure of Potential required for Standard Spark.	
10	496	510	14	13	47·70	
	498	”	12			
	497	”	13			
	495	”	15			
	497	”	13			
	496	”	14			
	498	”	12			
7·5	502	”	8	8		
	502	”	8			
	502	”	8			
	501	”	9			
	502	”	8			
	504	”	6			
8·75	502	”	8			
	500	”	10	10		
	500	”	10			
499·5	”	10·5				
						39·75